

Calculating the GAIA nominal scanning law

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SAG-LL-35

ABSTRACT. A method to calculate the Nominal Scanning Law (NSL) for GAIA is presented and a fortran implementation provided. The resulting NSL is given in tabular form, using quaternion representation, from which instantaneous values can be obtained by cubic spline interpolation.

1 Introduction

The nominal scanning law (NSL) proposed for GAIA is described in SAG-LL-014, 014A and 026, although without giving details of the practical calculation. In SAG-LL-30 an attitude parameterization using quaternions was suggested. In the present document these ideas are combined, so that the nominal scanning law is accurately computed in quaternion form ($\mathbf{q}$) as function of time for arbitrary scanning law parameters. This is done by numerical integration of the differential equations for the heliotropic angles ν and Ω , given the requirements of constant precession velocity and constant inertial spin rate about the $\mathbf{z}$ axis, followed by a transformation to $\mathbf{q}$.

The main limitation of the present treatment is that the motion of the satellite with respect to the Lagrange point L2 is not taken into account: the $\mathbf{z}$ axis revolves around a direction defined by the apparent sun as seen from the Earth (or L2), not from the actual position of the satellite. The maximum solar parallax in the L2 orbit is 9 arcmin. An important issue for further specification of the NSL is whether this parallax needs to be taken into account, or if a variation in the solar angle by ± 9 arcmin is tolerable from the viewpoint of thermal stability.

Notations here are generally the same as in the previous notes.

2 Differential equations for the heliotropic angles

The NSL as described in SAG-LL-014 is defined by the following conditions:

1. The centre of revolution is the *nominal sun* direction $\mathbf{s}$ which is assumed to be in the ecliptic ($\beta_s = 0$) with apparent longitude λ_s . (The apparent direction takes into account aberration, which amounts to about 20 arcsec.)
2. At any time the $\mathbf{z}$ axis is at the constant angle ξ from $\mathbf{s}$. For GAIA, the current choice is $\xi = 55$ deg.

3. The revolving phase $\nu(t)$ is continually increasing in such a way that $S = |\mathrm{d}\mathbf{z}/\mathrm{d}\lambda_s|$ is a constant. S must be chosen large enough that the loops described by the $\mathbf{z}$ axis on the sky overlap. For $\xi = 55$ deg a suitable choice is $S = 4.035$. The actual speed of the $\mathbf{z}$ axis with respect to the stars varies from 3.9105 to 4.0435 deg day⁻¹; this is also the maximum transverse velocity of the stars across the field of view.
4. The spin phase $\Omega(t)$ is chosen to make the z component of the inertial spin vector $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ strictly constant. The current choice is $\omega_z = 120$ arcsec s⁻¹.

The NSL is then completely specified by the apparent solar ephemeris $\lambda_s(t)$, the constants ξ , S and ω_z , and the initial values ν_0 , Ω_0 at time t_0 .

With $[\mathbf{l} \ \mathbf{j} \ \mathbf{k}]$ denoting the ecliptic triad we have

$$\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{l} \cos \lambda_s + \mathbf{j} \sin \lambda_s, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{j} = \mathbf{m} \cos \epsilon + \mathbf{n} \sin \epsilon$. The sun's apparent motion causes an inertial rotation at the rate $\dot{\lambda}_s$ about the axis $\mathbf{k} = \mathbf{n} \cos \epsilon - \mathbf{m} \sin \epsilon$. Here ϵ is the obliquity of the equator, taken to be exactly 23° 26' 21.448". The changes in ν and Ω cause further rotation of the telescope frame. The total inertial rotation of the telescope is therefore

$$\boldsymbol{\omega} = \mathbf{k} \dot{\lambda}_s + \mathbf{s} \dot{\nu} + \mathbf{z} \dot{\Omega}. \quad (2)$$

The precessional motion of the $\mathbf{z}$ axis is

$$\dot{\mathbf{z}} = \boldsymbol{\omega} \times \mathbf{z} = (\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{z}) \dot{\lambda}_s + (\mathbf{s} \times \mathbf{z}) \dot{\nu}. \quad (3)$$

Using that $|\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{z}|^2 = \cos^2 \beta_z = 1 - \sin^2 \xi \sin^2 \nu$, $|\mathbf{s} \times \mathbf{z}|^2 = \sin^2 \xi$ and $(\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{z})'(\mathbf{s} \times \mathbf{z}) = -\cos \xi \sin \xi \sin \nu$ we find

$$|\dot{\mathbf{z}}|^2 = (\dot{\lambda}_s \cos \nu)^2 + (\dot{\nu} \sin \xi - \dot{\lambda}_s \cos \xi \sin \nu)^2. \quad (4)$$

Thus for constant $S = |\dot{\mathbf{z}}| \dot{\lambda}_s^{-1}$ we have

$$\dot{\nu} = \dot{\lambda}_s \frac{\pm \sqrt{S^2 - \cos^2 \nu} + \cos \xi \sin \nu}{\sin \xi}. \quad (5)$$

The sign of the square root determines the sense of the revolution around $\mathbf{s}$; subsequently we adopt the positive sign (increasing ν).

For constant inertial spin rate about the $\mathbf{z}$ axis we obtain from Eq. (2)

$$\dot{\Omega} = \omega_z - \dot{\nu} \cos \xi - \dot{\lambda}_s \sin \xi \sin \nu. \quad (6)$$

Equations (5) and (6) are ordinary first-order differential equations which can be integrated from the initial conditions $\nu(t_0) = \nu_0$ and $\Omega(t_0) = \Omega_0$ by standard numerical methods. In the attached fortran programme `ns1q.f` (Appendix A) this is done using the Bulirsch-Stoer algorithm from *Numerical Recipes*, 2nd edition (Press et al. 1992).

3 Quaternion representation

The transformation from the celestial (equatorial) frame $[\mathbf{l} \ \mathbf{m} \ \mathbf{n}]$ to the telescope frame $[\mathbf{x} \ \mathbf{y} \ \mathbf{z}]$ is done by a sequence of elementary rotations involving the angles ϵ , λ_s , ν , ξ , and Ω . The corresponding quaternion representation of the attitude, $\mathbf{q}$, is given by Eq. (6) in SAG-LL-30. It is convenient to compute at the same time the time derivative $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$, for which an expression analogous to (8) in SAG-LL-30 is used, viz.:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\omega_n & +\omega_m & +\omega_l \\ +\omega_n & 0 & -\omega_l & +\omega_m \\ -\omega_m & +\omega_l & 0 & +\omega_n \\ -\omega_l & -\omega_m & -\omega_n & 0 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{q}. \quad (7)$$

The celestial components of $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ are computed from Eq. (2). For this we need the celestial components of $\mathbf{z}$, which are given by the third row of the attitude matrix $\mathbf{A}$, see Eq. (7) in SAG-LL-30.

The programme `ns1q.f` produces an output file in which the components of $\mathbf{q}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ are tabulated at regular intervals in t . Figure 1 shows the evolution of $\mathbf{q}(t)$ for an interval of 80 days, which spans a little more than one revolution of $\mathbf{z}$ around the sun. As seen in Fig. 2 each of the components varies almost sinusoidally with a period of approximately 6 hours (twice the spin period) and a slowly varying amplitude.

One detail concerning the integration/transformation is worth pointing out. In the integration of $\dot{\nu}$ and $\dot{\Omega}$ it is necessary, for numerical accuracy, to prevent the angles from becoming too large. If this is not done, then after 5 years (say), Ω has increased to nearly 10^5 rad, with a corresponding loss of 4–5 decimals in the numerical representation. The angles are of course only meaningful modulo 2π , so it is natural to convert them to the basic interval $[0, 2\pi)$. This, however, introduces discontinuities in $\mathbf{q}$ because the quaternion is defined in terms of *half* the elementary rotation angle [cf. Eq. (5) in SAG-LL-30]. To avoid this, one should only modify these angles by multiples of 4π . In `ns1q.f` the angles are kept in the interval $[-2\pi, 2\pi]$ by subtracting 4π when necessary. The resulting $\mathbf{q}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ are then completely smooth functions of time.

4 Cubic spline approximation

The actual attitude of GAIA may be represented by cubic splines in each of the four components of $\mathbf{q}$. This has the advantage of continuous first and second derivatives, which is physically realistic except at isolated points of micrometeoroid impacts. Such an impact causes a sudden change in the attitude rates, which however can be accommodated by inserting a multiple knot at the estimated time of impact.

The optimal interval Δt between knots (in the absence of significant impacts) is a compromise between the positional accuracy of the observations and the level of unmodelled line-of-sight perturbations. The effective variance of the astrometric observations per interval decreases with the interval length as $\Delta t^{-1/2}$ and goes to infinity as $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$. The

FIGURE 1. Evolution of the four components of the attitude vector $\mathbf{q}(t)$ over 80 days for $\xi = 55$ deg, $S = 4.035$ and $\omega_z = 120$ arcsec s^{-1} . The time is relative to the epoch J2000.0, and the initial angles are $\nu_0 = \Omega_0 = 0$. The slightly uneven envelope is caused by sampling effects from the time step used (0.01 day).

FIGURE 2. Same as Fig. 1 but only for the first day in order to show the phase shifts between the components and their quasi-sinusoidal shapes.

variance of unmodelled perturbations, on the other hand, is roughly given by the integral of the PSD above the Nyquist frequency $1/2\Delta t$, and increases indefinitely with Δt . There is consequently an optimal interval length where the total variance is minimized. For typical star densities and the PSD in Fig. 4.10b of the GAIA Study Report the optimal Δt should be around 15 s.

If the cubic spline approximation is chosen for the actual attitude, it may be convenient to use the same type of approximation for the nominal attitude. This guarantees that no unphysical discontinuities are introduced in the NSL due to the numerical representation. However, a longer Δt than 15 s could possibly be used for the nominal attitude. An important issue is then how accurate the NSL spline approximation is as function of Δt .

To answer this question, one day of scanning was computed by integrating the differential equations with a relatively small time step of 0.0001 day (8.64 s). Cubic splines were then fitted to every n th point in this table (cf. Appendix B), and the interpolated spline values were compared with the ‘true’ values from the integration. This was done for all eight components of $\mathbf{q}$ and $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$. The resulting maximum deviations (δ) were rather accurately described by the formulae:

$$|\delta q_i| \leq 800\Delta t^4 \quad (8)$$

$$|\delta \dot{q}_i| \leq 2500\Delta t^3 \quad [\text{day}^{-1}] \quad (9)$$

$$|\delta \omega_z| \leq 340,000\Delta t^4 \quad [\text{arcsec s}^{-1}] \quad (10)$$

where Δt is in days and $\delta \omega_z$ is the error in the computed spin rate (i.e. the deviation from 120 arcsec s^{-1}).

For $\Delta t = 15$ s this gives a maximum approximation error in pointing of 0.30 μas and in the rates of 0.12 $\mu\text{as s}^{-1}$. In ω_z the maximum error is 0.0003 $\mu\text{as s}^{-1}$. Clearly this is a more than adequate approximation. In practice a longer interval of (say) 0.001 day (86.4 s) could just as well be used for the NSL. The total size of the NSL file for a five year mission would then be around 120 MB.

Considering the quasi-harmonic nature of the components $q_i(t)$ it is likely that a more compact approximation of the NSL could be derived in terms of trigonometric functions. If some kind of trigonometric interpolation is used, it is not obvious however how one could guarantee continuity of the interpolated function and its first two derivatives.

5 Direct integration of $\mathbf{q}(t)$

For completeness I would like to mention that the quaternion form of the NSL can be integrated directly without using the heliographic angles as an intermediary. This may be the preferred method if the solar parallax in the L2 orbit must be taken into account, since in that case the definition of ν and Ω is no longer so simple. The kinematic equations for

$\mathbf{q}(t)$ [Eq. (8) in SAG-LL-30] reads:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & +\omega_z & -\omega_y & +\omega_x \\ -\omega_z & 0 & +\omega_x & +\omega_y \\ +\omega_y & -\omega_x & 0 & +\omega_z \\ -\omega_x & -\omega_y & -\omega_z & 0 \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{q}. \quad (11)$$

In order to integrate these equations, it is necessary to write $(\omega_x, \omega_y, \omega_z)$ as explicit functions of $\mathbf{s}$, $\dot{\mathbf{s}}$ and $\mathbf{q}$. For ω_z that is trivial because it is a constant. ω_x and ω_y on the other hand must satisfy two conditions. The first is set by the prescribed precessional speed $|\dot{\mathbf{z}}|$, since $\omega_x^2 + \omega_y^2 = |\dot{\mathbf{z}}|^2$. The second condition is that $\mathbf{z}'\mathbf{s} = \cos \xi = \text{constant}$, which by differentiation gives $(\mathbf{x}'\mathbf{s})\omega_y - (\mathbf{y}'\mathbf{s})\omega_x + \mathbf{z}'\dot{\mathbf{s}} = 0$. The two conditions therefore define a circle and a straight line, respectively, in the (ω_x, ω_y) plane. If the radius of the circle is large enough (which is always the case for the NSL) there are two intersections corresponding to opposite senses of revolution about $\mathbf{s}$. The intersections are obtained by solving a second-order algebraic equation with real roots. The sense of revolution is given by the sign of $\dot{\mathbf{z}}'(\mathbf{s} \times \mathbf{z}) = (\mathbf{x}'\mathbf{s})\omega_x + (\mathbf{y}'\mathbf{s})\omega_y$. Thus it is a simple matter to select the root corresponding to a certain sense of revolution. Specifically,

$$\omega_x = \frac{\pm(\mathbf{x}'\mathbf{s})\sqrt{(|\dot{\mathbf{z}}|\sin\xi)^2 - (\mathbf{z}'\dot{\mathbf{s}})^2} + (\mathbf{y}'\mathbf{s})(\mathbf{z}'\dot{\mathbf{s}})}{\sin^2\xi}, \quad (12)$$

$$\omega_y = \frac{\pm(\mathbf{y}'\mathbf{s})\sqrt{(|\dot{\mathbf{z}}|\sin\xi)^2 - (\mathbf{z}'\dot{\mathbf{s}})^2} - (\mathbf{x}'\mathbf{s})(\mathbf{z}'\dot{\mathbf{s}})}{\sin^2\xi}, \quad (13)$$

where upper/lower sign corresponds to positive/negative revolution (same sign as $\dot{\nu}$).

This method to integrate the NSL has not been tested in practice. While it seems elegant in principle, there are several reasons for expecting it to be less accurate than integration of (ν, Ω) : first, the quasi-harmonic behaviour of $\mathbf{q}$ suggests that higher-order derivatives may be more important than for ν and Ω (which increase roughly linearly with time); second, there is no implicit guarantee that the constant values of ξ and $|\mathbf{q}|$ are preserved; and finally, the four coupled equations for $\mathbf{q}$ may be inherently less stable than the two for (ν, Ω) . It is also somewhat awkward to set up the initial $\mathbf{q}(t_0)$ without resorting to a sequence of rotations similar to the heliotropic angles.

6 Appendices

Appendix A contains a fortran implementation of the method described in Sections 2 and 3. It produces a text file with $\mathbf{q}(t)$ and $\dot{\mathbf{q}}(t)$ for a regular time sequence.

Appendix B contains fortran routines for cubic spline interpolation. These can be used to calculate the instantaneous NSL from a table such as produced by the program in Appendix A.

All files are available by anonymous ftp at
<ftp://nastol.astro.lu.se/incoming/lennart/GAIA-LL-35-dir/>

Appendix A. Numerical integration of the NSL

Various constants are defined in the following three INCLUDE files:

```
-----
c This is 'const_math.h'
c Mathematical constants and general units
c
  REAL*8 pi, pihalf, twopi, fourpi, deg, arcsec, sec
  PARAMETER (pi = 3.14159265358979324d0,
+           pihalf = pi/2d0,
+           twopi = 2d0*pi,
+           fourpi = 4d0*pi,
+           deg = pi/180d0,
+           arcsec = deg/3600d0,
+           sec = 1d0/86400d0)
-----
c This is 'const_astr.h'
c Astronomical and physical constants
c
  REAL*8 clight, au, gs, obliq
  PARAMETER (clight = 299792458d0,
+           au = 1.495978701d11,
+           gs = 1.32712438d20,
+           obliq = 0.409092804222329d0)
-----
c This is 'const_nsl.h'
c Constants for the Nominal Scanning Law (NSL)
c Requires prior inclusion of const_math.h
c
  REAL*8 xi_nsl, s_nsl, oz_nsl
  PARAMETER (xi_nsl = 55d0*deg,
+           s_nsl = 4.035d0,
+           oz_nsl = 120d0*arcsec/sec)
```

The following fortran program computes the NSL for the time sequence defined by the variables `t0`, `dt`, and `tmax`. To compile the program, the include files above and the subroutine package `qn_subs.f` are also needed.

```
-----
c This is nslq.f
c
  PROGRAM nslq
c
c GAIA Nominal Scanning Law (NSL)
c
c This program calculates the NSL for GAIA by direct integration
c of the kinematic equations for (nearly) constant precession rate
c of the z axis and (strictly) constant spin rate about the z axis.
c
c The nominal attitude is computed for the discrete times
c t = t0, t0+dt, t0+2*dt, ... tmax
c and the results are written to file 'nslq.prn' in quaternion
c representation. There are 9 columns with t, q(1:4), q1(1:4)
c where q = quaternion wrt the equatorial reference frame,
c q1 = time derivative of q. t is reckoned in days from J2000.
c
c The following parameters determine the scanning law:
c xi_nsl = strictly constant angle between the z axis and the
c 'nominal sun' direction (see limitations below)
```

```

c  s_nsl      = strictly constant ratio between the inertial rate of
c              change of the z axis direction and the nominal solar
c              longitude; s_nsl .GE. 0.247+4.401*sinc(xi_nsl) is
c              required for 'loop overlap' (see SAG-LL-14)
c  oz_nsl     = strictly constant inertial spin rate about z axis
c  t0         = initial time in days from J2000
c  anu0       = initial revolving phase in rad
c  bigom0     = initial spin phase in rad
c  The first three parameters are specified in 'const_nsl.h' (shared
c  by several subroutines), the last three are defined in this program.
c
c  Limitations:
c
c  The orbital motion of GAIA with respect to the L2 point is
c  neglected, and the 'nominal sun' direction is simply given by
c  the ecliptic coordinates (slon,0). Here slon is the approximate
c  geocentric apparent solar longitude provided by subroutine sun.
c
c  Reference: GAIA-LL-35 (L Lindegren, 2001 Feb 19)
c
c  Subroutines used:
c  sun         = approximate apparent solar ephemeris
c  mod4pi     = adjust argument by multiple of 4*pi
c  nsl_h2q    = convert from heliotropic angles to quaternion
c  nsl_der    = derivative subroutine (for bsstep)
c  bsstep     = Bulirsch-Stoer algorithm (calling mmid and pzextr)
c  qn_*       = quaternion subroutines (from qn_subs.f)
c
c  Other dependences:
c  const_math.h, const_astr.h, const_nsl.h = include files
c  qn_subs.f = quaternion subroutine package (v1 or higher)
c
c      IMPLICIT NONE
c
c      INCLUDE 'const_math.h'
c      INCLUDE 'const_astr.h'
c      INCLUDE 'const_nsl.h'
c
c      REAL*8 q(4), q1(4)
c      REAL*8 eps, htry, hdid, hnext
c      REAL*8 t0, dt, tmax, told, tnew, anu0, bigom0
c      REAL*8 y(2), dydt(2), yscal(2)
c      INTEGER nt, it
c      EXTERNAL nsl_der
c
c  Define and open output file:
c
c      OPEN(10,file='nslq.prn')
c
c  Define time sequence for output:
c
c      t0 = 0d0
c      dt = 0.001d0
c      tmax = 1d0
c
c  Define initial revolving phase and spin phase:
c
c      anu0 = 0d0
c      bigom0 = 0d0
c
c  Constants for integrator bsstep:
c
c      yscal(1) = 1d0
c      yscal(2) = 1d0
c      eps = 1d-15
c
c  Initialization of variables:
c

```

```

        told = t0
        y(1) = anu0
        y(2) = bigom0
        nt = nint(tmax/dt)
c
c   Time loop:
c
      DO it = 0, nt
        tnew = t0 + dble(it)*dt
        IF (it .EQ. 0) GOTO 200
100    CONTINUE
        htry = tnew - told
        CALL bsstep(y,dydt,2,told,htry,eps,yscal,hdid,hnext,nsl_der)
        IF (hdid .LT. htry) THEN
          PRINT *, 'warning: htry, hdid =',htry,hdid
          CALL nsl_der(told, y, dydt)
          GOTO 100
        ENDIF
        CALL mod4pi(y(1))
        CALL mod4pi(y(2))
200    CONTINUE
        CALL nsl_der(tnew, y, dydt)
        CALL nsl_h2q(tnew, y, dydt,      q, q1)
        WRITE(*,'(x,f11.6,4f8.4,4f9.4)') tnew, q, q1
        WRITE(10,'(x,f11.6,8f21.16)') tnew, q, q1
      ENDDO
      CLOSE(10)
      END
c*****
      SUBROUTINE sun(t,  sdis, slon, slon1)
c*****
c
c   Calculates the approximate solar distance [au] and apparent
c   longitude [rad] as functions of time [days from J2000.0].
c   Also returns the derivative slon1 = d(slon)/dt [rad/day].
c
c   a is the mean longitude relative to the fixed equinox 2000,
c   decreased by the mean aberration in longitude (20.496 arcsec)
c   g is the mean anomaly
c
c   LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 Feb 12
c
      IMPLICIT NONE
      REAL*8 t, sdis, slon, slon1
c
      INCLUDE 'const_math.h'
c
      REAL*8 e, e2, e3, e4, a0, a1, g0, g1, a, g, s1g, s2g, c1g, c2g
      PARAMETER (e = 0.016709d0, e2=2d0*e, e3=1.25d0*e*e, e4=e*e/2d0)
      PARAMETER (a0 = 280.458d0*deg, a1 = 0.98560911d0*deg)
      PARAMETER (g0 = 357.528d0*deg, g1 = 0.98560028d0*deg)
c
      a = a0 + a1*t
      g = g0 + g1*t
      s1g = dsin(g)
      s2g = dsin(2d0*g)
      c1g = dcos(g)
      c2g = dcos(2d0*g)
      slon = a + e2*s1g + e3*s2g
      sdis = 1d0 - e*dcos(g + e*s1g + e4*s2g)
      slon1 = a1 + (e2*c1g + 2d0*e3*c2g)*g1
c
      RETURN
      END
c*****
      SUBROUTINE mod4pi(x)
c*****
c

```

```

c  Modifies the angle x by adding a multiple of 4*pi
c  so that, on output, -2*pi .LT. x .LE. 2*pi
c
      IMPLICIT NONE
      REAL*8 x
      INCLUDE 'const_math.h'
      x = x - fourpi*dnint(x/fourpi)
      RETURN
      END
c*****
      SUBROUTINE nsl_h2q(t, y, dydt, q, q1)
c*****
c
c  Convert heliotropic angles and rates in (y,dydt) to
c  quaternion representation (q,q1)
c
c  INPUT:
c
c  t          = time in days from J2000
c  y(1:2)     = vector containing the angles nu and Omega [rad]
c  dydt(1:2)  = vector containing the time derivatives of nu and Omega
c              [rad/day] at time t: dydt(1) = d(nu)/dt, etc
c
c  OUTPUT:
c
c  q(1:4)     = quaternion representing the attitude at time t
c  q1(1:4)    = time derivative of q(1:4) [1/day]
c
c  Other data needed by nsl_h2q are:
c  xi_nsl = revolving angle (transferred in const_nsl.h).
c  nsl_der calls the subroutine sun to get slon = solar longitude
c  and slon1 = time derivative of slon.
c
c  Reference: SAG-LL-30
c
c  LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 Feb 14
c
      IMPLICIT NONE
      REAL*8 t, y(2), dydt(2), q(4), q1(4)
c
      INCLUDE 'const_math.h'
      INCLUDE 'const_nsl.h'
      INCLUDE 'const_astr.h'
c
      LOGICAL first
      REAL*8 qe(4), qs(4), qn(4), qx(4), qo(4), qes(4), qesn(4),
+         qesnx(4), amat(3,3), ecl(3,3), scel(3)
      REAL*8 sdis, slon, slon1, cslon, sslon
      INTEGER i
      DATA first/.TRUE./
      SAVE first, qe, qx, ecl
c
c  On first call, set up the fixed quaternions qe and qx,
c  and the 3*3 matrix defining the ecliptical triad ecl:
c
      IF (first) THEN
          CALL qn_a2q(obliq, 1, qe)
          CALL qn_a2q(pihalf-xi_nsl, 2, qx)
          CALL qn_q2mat(qe, ecl)
          first = .FALSE.
      ENDIF
c
c  Set up the remaining elementary quaternions qs, qn, qo:
c
      CALL sun(t, sdis, slon, slon1)
      CALL qn_a2q(slon, 3, qs)
      CALL qn_a2q(y(1)-pihalf, 1, qn)
      CALL qn_a2q(y(2), 3, qo)

```

```

c
c Compute total quaternion q = qe.qs.qn.qx.qo :
c
    CALL qn_mult(qe, qs,  qes)
    CALL qn_mult(qes, qn,  qesn)
    CALL qn_mult(qesn, qx,  qesnx)
    CALL qn_mult(qesnx, qo,  q)
c
c Compute attitude matrix amat:
c
    CALL qn_q2mat(q, amat)
c
c Compute the spin vector in celestial system scel(1:3):
c
    cslon = dcos(sl原因)
    sslon = dsin(sl原因)
    DO i = 1, 3
        scel(i) = ecl(3,i)*slon1 + (ecl(1,i)*cslon + ecl(2,i)*sslon)
    +           *dydt(1) + amat(3,i)*dydt(2)
    ENDDO
c
c Compute the rates in quaternion components (SAG-LL-35, Eq. 7):
c
    q1(1) = 0.5d0*(-scel(3)*q(2) + scel(2)*q(3) + scel(1)*q(4))
    q1(2) = 0.5d0*(+scel(3)*q(1) - scel(1)*q(3) + scel(2)*q(4))
    q1(3) = 0.5d0*(-scel(2)*q(1) + scel(1)*q(2) + scel(3)*q(4))
    q1(4) = 0.5d0*(-scel(1)*q(1) - scel(2)*q(2) - scel(3)*q(3))
c
    RETURN
    END
c*****
c      SUBROUTINE nsl_der(t, y, dydt)
c*****
c
c Computes the time derivatives of the heliotropic angles nu and Omega
c according to the Nominal Scanning Law
c
c INPUT:
c
c t          = time in days from J2000
c y(1:2)     = vector containing the angles nu and Omega [rad]
c             at time t: y(1) = nu; y(2) = Omega
c
c OUTPUT:
c
c dydt(1:2) = vector containing the time derivatives of nu and Omega
c             [rad/day] at time t: dydt(1) = d(nu)/dt, etc
c
c This subroutine is used by bsstep to integrate (nu,Omega) as
c function of t, and for this reason the arguments are fixed.
c Other data needed by nsl_der to compute the derivatives are:
c xi_nsl = revolving angle, s_nsl = d|zdot|/d(sl原因) = the speed of
c z motion on the sky, relative to the solar longitude rate, and
c oz_nsl = the fixed inertial rotation about the z axis. These data
c are transferred to nsl_der via parameters in const_nsl.h .
c nsl_der calls the subroutine sun to get slon = solar longitude.
c
c Reference: SAG-LL-14
c
c LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 Feb 14
c
    IMPLICIT NONE
    REAL*8 t, y(2), dydt(2)
c
    INCLUDE 'const_math.h'
    INCLUDE 'const_nsl.h'
c
    LOGICAL first

```

```

REAL*8 s2, cxi, sxi, cnu, snu, sdis, slon, slon1
DATA first/.TRUE./
SAVE first, cxi, sxi
c
IF (first) THEN
    s2 = s_nsl**2
    cxi = dcos(xi_nsl)
    sxi = dsin(xi_nsl)
    first = .FALSE.
ENDIF
c
CALL sun(t, sdis, slon, slon1)
cnu = dcos(y(1))
snu = dsin(y(1))
dydt(1) = slon1*(dsqrt(s2 - cnu**2) + cxi*snu)/sxi
dydt(2) = oz_nsl - cxi*dydt(1) - sxi*snu*slon1
c
RETURN
END
c
c This is bsstep.for from Numerical recipes, 2nd ed.
c
c*****
SUBROUTINE bsstep(y,dydx,nv,x,htry,eps,yscal,hdid,hnext,derivs)
c*****
IMPLICIT NONE
INTEGER nv,NMAX,KMAXX,IMAX
REAL*8 eps,hdid,hnext,htry,x,dydx(nv),y(nv),yscal(nv),SAFE1,SAFE2,
*REDMAX,REDMIN,TINY,SCALMX
PARAMETER (NMAX=50,KMAXX=8,IMAX=KMAXX+1,SAFE1=.25d0,SAFE2=.7d0,
*REDMAX=1d-5,REDMIN=.7d0,TINY=1d-30,SCALMX=.1d0)
CU USES derivs,mmid,pzextr
INTEGER i,iq,k,km,kmax,kopt,nseq(IMAX)
REAL*8 eps1,epsold,errmax,fact,h,red,scale,work,wrkmin,xest,xnew,
*a(IMAX),alf(KMAXX,KMAXX),err(KMAXX),yerr(NMAX),ysav(NMAX),
*yseq(NMAX)
LOGICAL first,reduct
SAVE a,alf,epsold,first,kmax,kopt,nseq,xnew
EXTERNAL derivs
DATA first/.true./,epsold/-1./
DATA nseq /2,4,6,8,10,12,14,16,18/
if(eps.ne.epsold)then
    hnext=-1d29
    xnew=-1d29
    eps1=SAFE1*eps
    a(1)=nseq(1)+1
    do 11 k=1,KMAXX
        a(k+1)=a(k)+nseq(k+1)
11    continue
    do 13 iq=2,KMAXX
        do 12 k=1,iq-1
            alf(k,iq)=eps1**((a(k+1)-a(iq+1))/((a(iq+1)-a(1)+1d0)*(2*k+
*1)))
12    continue
13    continue
    epsold=eps
    do 14 kopt=2,KMAXX-1
        if(a(kopt+1).gt.a(kopt)*alf(kopt-1,kopt))goto 1
14    continue
1    kmax=kopt
endif
h=htry
do 15 i=1,nv
    ysav(i)=y(i)
15    continue
if(h.ne.hnext.or.x.ne.xnew)then
    first=.true.
    kopt=kmax

```

```

endif
reduct=.false.
2 do 17 k=1,kmax
  xnew=x+h
  if(xnew.eq.x)pause 'step size underflow in bsstep'
  call mmid(ysav,dydx,nv,x,h,nseq(k),yseq,derivs)
  xest=(h/nseq(k))**2
  call pzextr(k,xest,yseq,y,yerr,nv)
  if(k.ne.1)then
    errmax=TINY
    do 16 i=1,nv
      errmax=dmax1(errmax,dabs(yerr(i)/yscal(i)))
16 continue
    errmax=errmax/eps
    km=k-1
    err(km)=(errmax/SAFE1)**(1d0/(2*km+1))
  endif
  if(k.ne.1.and.(k.ge.kopt-1.or.first))then
    if(errmax.lt.1d0)goto 4
    if(k.eq.kmax.or.k.eq.kopt+1)then
      red=SAFE2/err(km)
      goto 3
    else if(k.eq.kopt)then
      if(alf(kopt-1,kopt).lt.err(km))then
        red=1./err(km)
        goto 3
      endif
    else if(kopt.eq.kmax)then
      if(alf(km,kmax-1).lt.err(km))then
        red=alf(km,kmax-1)*SAFE2/err(km)
        goto 3
      endif
    else if(alf(km,kopt).lt.err(km))then
      red=alf(km,kopt-1)/err(km)
      goto 3
    endif
  endif
17 continue
3 red=dmin1(red,REDMIN)
  red=dmax1(red,REDMAX)
  h=h*red
  reduct=.true.
  goto 2
4 x=xnew
  hdid=h
  first=.false.
  wrkmin=1d35
  do 18 kk=1,km
    fact=dmax1(err(kk),SCALMX)
    work=fact*a(kk+1)
    if(work.lt.wrkmin)then
      scale=fact
      wrkmin=work
      kopt=kk+1
    endif
18 continue
  hnext=h/scale
  if(kopt.ge.k.and.kopt.ne.kmax.and..not.reduct)then
    fact=dmax1(scale/alf(kopt-1,kopt),SCALMX)
    if(a(kopt+1)*fact.le.wrkmin)then
      hnext=h/fact
      kopt=kopt+1
    endif
  endif
endif
return
END

```

c

c This is mmid.for from Numerical recipes, 2nd ed.

```

c
c*****
      SUBROUTINE mmid(y,dydx,nvar,xs,htot,nstep,yout,derivs)
c*****
      IMPLICIT NONE
      INTEGER nstep,nvar,NMAX
      REAL*8 htot,xs,dydx(nvar),y(nvar),yout(nvar)
      EXTERNAL derivs
      PARAMETER (NMAX=50)
      INTEGER i,n
      REAL*8 h,h2,swap,x,ym(NMAX),yn(NMAX)
      h=htot/nstep
      do 11 i=1,nvar
         ym(i)=y(i)
         yn(i)=y(i)+h*dydx(i)
11      continue
         x=xs+h
         call derivs(x,yn,yout)
         h2=2d0*h
         do 13 n=2,nstep
            do 12 i=1,nvar
               swap=ym(i)+h2*yout(i)
               ym(i)=yn(i)
               yn(i)=swap
12          continue
               x=x+h
               call derivs(x,yn,yout)
13          continue
            do 14 i=1,nvar
               yout(i)=0.5d0*(ym(i)+yn(i)+h*yout(i))
14          continue
            return
         END
c
c This is pzextr.for from Numerical recipes, 2nd ed.
c
c*****
      SUBROUTINE pzextr(iest,xest,yest,yz,dy,nv)
c*****
      IMPLICIT NONE
      INTEGER iest,nv,IMAX,NMAX
      REAL*8 xest,dy(nv),yest(nv),yz(nv)
      PARAMETER (IMAX=13,NMAX=50)
      INTEGER j,k1
      REAL*8 delta,f1,f2,q,d(NMAX),qcol(NMAX,IMAX),x(IMAX)
      SAVE qcol,x
      x(iest)=xest
      do 11 j=1,nv
         dy(j)=yest(j)
         yz(j)=yest(j)
11      continue
         if(iest.eq.1) then
            do 12 j=1,nv
               qcol(j,1)=yest(j)
12          continue
         else
            do 13 j=1,nv
               d(j)=yest(j)
13          continue
            do 15 k1=1,iest-1
               delta=1d0/(x(iest-k1)-xest)
               f1=xest*delta
               f2=x(iest-k1)*delta
               do 14 j=1,nv
                  q=qcol(j,k1)
                  qcol(j,k1)=dy(j)
                  delta=d(j)-q
                  dy(j)=f1*delta

```

```

                d(j)=f2*delta
                yz(j)=yz(j)+dy(j)
14          continue
15          continue
            do 16 j=1,nv
                qcol(j,iest)=dy(j)
16          continue
            endif
            return
            END

```

The following file contains subroutines for various transformations involving quaternions.

```

c-----
c This is qn_subs.f
c Quaternion subroutines, v1
c
c*****
c      SUBROUTINE qn_a2q(a, iax,  q)
c*****
c
c Quaternion subroutine:  conversion angle to quaternion
c
c Returns the quaternion q(1:4) representing rotation
c by angle a [rad] about axis iax [= 1, 2, or 3]
c
c Reference: Eq. (5) in SAG-LL-30
c
c LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 Feb 12
c
c      IMPLICIT NONE
c      REAL*8 a, q(4)
c      INTEGER iax
c
c      REAL*8 halfa
c      INTEGER i
c
c      IF (iax .LT. 1 .OR. iax .GT. 3) THEN
c          PRINT *, 'qn_a2q: improper iax = ', iax
c          STOP
c      ENDIF
c
c      halfa = a/2d0
c      q(4) = dcos(halfa)
c      DO i = 1, 3
c          q(i) = 0d0
c      ENDDO
c      q(iax) = dsin(halfa)
c
c      RETURN
c      END
c*****
c      SUBROUTINE qn_mult(q1, q2,  q3)
c*****
c
c Quaternion subroutine:  multiplication q3 = q1 * q2
c
c Returns the quaternion q3(1:4) representing the two
c successive rotations q1(1:4) and q2(1:4)
c
c Reference: Eq. (4) in SAG-LL-30
c
c LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 Feb 12
c
c      IMPLICIT NONE
c      REAL*8 q1(4), q2(4), q3(4)

```

```

c
q3(1) = q2(4)*q1(1) + q2(3)*q1(2) - q2(2)*q1(3) + q2(1)*q1(4)
q3(2) = -q2(3)*q1(1) + q2(4)*q1(2) + q2(1)*q1(3) + q2(2)*q1(4)
q3(3) = q2(2)*q1(1) - q2(1)*q1(2) + q2(4)*q1(3) + q2(3)*q1(4)
q3(4) = -q2(1)*q1(1) - q2(2)*q1(2) - q2(3)*q1(3) + q2(4)*q1(4)
c
RETURN
END
c*****
SUBROUTINE qn_q2stel(q, q1, stel)
c*****
c
c Quaternion subroutine: calculate spin vector in telescope frame
c
c Given the attitude q(1:4) and attitude rate q1(1:4) in quaternion
c form, this routine returns the inertial spin rate stel(1:3) wrt
c the telescope frame
c
c Reference: Eq. (9) in SAG-LL-30
c
c LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 Feb 18
c
IMPLICIT NONE
REAL*8 q(4), q1(4), stel(4)
c
REAL*8 s2
s2 = 2d0/(q(1)**2 + q(2)**2 + q(3)**2 + q(4)**2)
stel(1) = (+q(4)*q1(1) + q(3)*q1(2) - q(2)*q1(3) - q(1)*q1(4))*s2
stel(2) = (-q(3)*q1(1) + q(4)*q1(2) + q(1)*q1(3) - q(2)*q1(4))*s2
stel(3) = (+q(2)*q1(1) - q(1)*q1(2) + q(4)*q1(3) - q(3)*q1(4))*s2
c
RETURN
END
c*****
SUBROUTINE qn_q2scl(q, q1, scl)
c*****
c
c Quaternion subroutine: calculate spin vector in celestial frame
c
c Given the attitude q(1:4) and attitude rate q1(1:4) in quaternion
c form, this routine returns the inertial spin rate scl(1:3) wrt
c the celestial frame
c
c Reference: Eq. (11) in SAG-LL-30
c
c LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 Feb 18
c
IMPLICIT NONE
REAL*8 q(4), q1(4), scl(4)
c
REAL*8 s2
s2 = 2d0/(q(1)**2 + q(2)**2 + q(3)**2 + q(4)**2)
scl(1) = (+q(4)*q1(1) - q(3)*q1(2) + q(2)*q1(3) - q(1)*q1(4))*s2
scl(2) = (+q(3)*q1(1) + q(4)*q1(2) - q(1)*q1(3) - q(2)*q1(4))*s2
scl(3) = (-q(2)*q1(1) + q(1)*q1(2) + q(4)*q1(3) - q(3)*q1(4))*s2
c
RETURN
END
c*****
SUBROUTINE qn_q2mat(q, amat)
c*****
c
c Quaternion subroutine: conversion quaternion to matrix
c
c Returns the attitude matrix amat(1:3,1:3)
c corresponding to the quaternion q(1:4)
c
c Reference: Eq. (7) in SAG-LL-30

```

```

c
c LL, Lund Observatory, 2001 Feb 12
c
  IMPLICIT NONE
  REAL*8 q(4), amat(3,3)
c
  REAL*8 q11, q12, q13, q14, q22, q23, q24, q33, q34, q44, s, s1, s2

  q11 = q(1)*q(1)
  q12 = q(1)*q(2)
  q13 = q(1)*q(3)
  q14 = q(1)*q(4)
  q22 = q(2)*q(2)
  q23 = q(2)*q(3)
  q24 = q(2)*q(4)
  q33 = q(3)*q(3)
  q34 = q(3)*q(4)
  q44 = q(4)*q(4)
  s = q11 + q22 + q33 + q44
  IF (s .LE. 0d0) THEN
    PRINT *, 'qn_q2mat: singular q'
    STOP
  ENDF
  s1 = 1d0/s
  s2 = 2d0*s1
  amat(1,1) = (q11 - q22 - q33 + q44)*s1
  amat(1,2) = (q12 + q34)*s2
  amat(1,3) = (q13 - q24)*s2
  amat(2,1) = (q12 - q34)*s2
  amat(2,2) = (-q11 + q22 - q33 + q44)*s1
  amat(2,3) = (q23 + q14)*s2
  amat(3,1) = (q13 + q24)*s2
  amat(3,2) = (q23 - q14)*s2
  amat(3,3) = (-q11 - q22 + q33 + q44)*s1
c
  RETURN
  END

```

Appendix B. Spline interpolation of the NSL

The following two subroutines, taken from *Numerical Recipes*, 2nd edition (Press et al. 1992)), can be used to interpolate the functions $q_k(t)$, $k = 1 \dots 4$ by means of cubic splines. If the data for n time steps are stored in the arrays $\mathbf{t}(1:n)$, $\mathbf{q}(1:n,1:4)$ and $\mathbf{q1}(1:n,1:4)$ (where $\mathbf{q1}$ contains the first derivatives), then use the following statements to compute the array $\mathbf{q2}(1:n,1:4)$ with second derivatives:

```

DO k = 1, 4
    CALL spline(t, q(1,k), n, q1(1,k), q1(n,k), q2(1,k))
ENDDO

```

This is done only once. Interpolation to arbitrary $\mathbf{tint}$ in the range from $\mathbf{t}(1)$ to $\mathbf{t}(n)$ is then done through the calls:

```

DO k = 1, 4
    CALL splint(t,q(1,k),q2(1,k),n,tint,qint(k),q1int(k),q2int(k))
ENDDO

```

The interpolated spline value and derivatives are stored in $\mathbf{qint}(1:4)$, $\mathbf{q1int}(1:4)$, and $\mathbf{q2int}(1:4)$.

```

c-----
c This is spl_subs.f
c Spline interpolation subroutines, v1
c
c*****
c      SUBROUTINE spline(x,y,n,yp1,ypn,y2)
c*****
c
c This is spline.for from Numerical Recipes
c
  INTEGER n,NMAX
  REAL*8 yp1,ypn,x(n),y(n),y2(n)
  PARAMETER (NMAX=10001)
  INTEGER i,k
  REAL*8 p,qn,sig,un,u(NMAX)
  IF (n .GT. NMAX) STOP 'NMAX too small in spline'
  if (yp1 .gt. 0.99d30) then
    y2(1)=0d0
    u(1)=0d0
  else
    y2(1)=-0.5d0
    u(1)=(3d0/(x(2)-x(1)))*((y(2)-y(1))/(x(2)-x(1))-yp1)
  endif
  do 11 i=2,n-1
    sig=(x(i)-x(i-1))/(x(i+1)-x(i-1))
    p=sig*y2(i-1)+2d0
    y2(i)=(sig-1d0)/p
    u(i)=(6d0*((y(i+1)-y(i))/(x(i+1)-x(i))-
*1-x(i))- (y(i)-y(i-1))/(x(i)-x(i-1)))/(x(i+1)-x(i-1))-sig*
*u(i-1))/p
11  continue
  if (ypn .gt. 0.99d30) then
    qn=0d0
    un=0d0
  else
    qn=0.5d0
    un=(3d0/(x(n)-x(n-1)))*(ypn-(y(n)-y(n-1))/(x(n)-x(n-1)))

```

```

endif
y2(n)=(un-qn*u(n-1))/(qn*y2(n-1)+1d0)
do 12 k=n-1,1,-1
  y2(k)=y2(k)*y2(k+1)+u(k)
12 continue
return
END
c*****
SUBROUTINE splint(xa,ya,y2a,n,x,y,yp,ypp)
c*****
c
c This is splint.for from Numerical Recipes
c
c Modified by L Lindegren:
c (1) yp, ypp = 1st and 2nd derivatives of spline at x added as output
c (2) y, yp and ypp set to 0 when x is outside range
c
INTEGER n
REAL*8 x,y,xa(n),y2a(n),ya(n),yp,ypp
INTEGER k,khi,klo
REAL*8 a,b,h
IF (x .LT. xa(1) .OR. x .GT. xa(n)) THEN
  y = 0d0
  yp = 0d0
  ypp = 0d0
  RETURN
ENDIF
klo=1
khi=n
1 if (khi-klo .gt. 1) then
  k=(khi+klo)/2
  if (xa(k) .gt. x) then
    khi=k
  else
    klo=k
  endif
  goto 1
endif
h=xa(khi)-xa(klo)
if (h .eq. 0d0) pause 'bad xa input in splint'
a=(xa(khi)-x)/h
b=(x-xa(klo))/h
y=a*ya(klo)+b*ya(khi)+((a**3-a)*y2a(klo)+(b**3-b)*y2a(khi))*(h**
*2)/6d0
yp = (ya(khi)-ya(klo))/h +
, (h/6d0) * ((3*b*b-1d0)*y2a(khi) - (3*a*a-1d0)*y2a(klo))
ypp = a*y2a(klo) + b*y2a(khi)
return
END

```